

Good Practices in Research Software Development

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Workshop: Unlocking the Potential of Open Research Software in Acoustics

Lessons learned from developing a room acoustic modelling research software in Python

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Workshop: Unlocking the Potential of Open Research Software in Acoustics

Outline

INTRODUCTION
(1MIN)

VERSION
CONTROL (8 MIN)

CODE QUALITY
(8MIN)

DOCUMENTATION
(2 MIN)

NEXT WORKSHOP
(0.5 MIN)

Version control

- What?
 - Version control systems are fundamental tools for software development, allowing us to track changes, revert to previous states, and manage contributions from multiple developers effectively.
- Why?
 - Version control ensures that every change to the codebase is documented, making it easier to debug issues and understand the evolution of the software.
 - A complete long-term change history of every file (keep things organized and at hand when you need them)
 - Branching and merging (collaborative/team work)
 - Traceability (project management).

“Piled Higher and Deeper” by Jorge Cham,
<http://www.phdcomics.com>

Main ingredients of using Git on your own [1]

1. Setting up a repository.
 - git init/clone/config/alias

```
credential.helper=osxkeychain
user.email=hqwang815@gmail.com
user.name=Huiqing Wang
core.editor=nano
core.excludesfile=~/.dotfiles/.gitignore_global
pull.rebase=true
branch.autosetuprebase=always
core.repositoryformatversion=0
core.filemode=true
core.bare=false
core.logallrefupdates=true
```

```
Apple ~/De/DG_RoomAcoustics on main_group
alias glgga
glgga='git log --graph --decorate --all'
```


Main ingredients of using Git on your own [1]

1. Setting up a repository.

- git init/clone/config/alias
- .gitattributes
 - Binary files
 - Merge Strategies: Specify custom merging strategies for specific files. This is useful for files that need to be merged in a particular way.

```
# Python data files
*.npy binary

# Matlab data files
*.mat binary

# Compiled Python files
*.pyc binary

# msh files of GMSH
*.msh binary
```


Main ingredients of using Git on your own [1]

1. Setting up a repository.

- git init/clone/config/alias
- .gitattributes
- .ignore
 - Ignored files are usually build artifacts and machine generated files that can be derived from your repository source or should otherwise not be committed.

```
# Mac
.DS_Store

# virtual environments
env
env3
venv
venv3

#test file
test_code/test_python.py
test_code/test_meshio
tests/dev_tests/*

# documentation examples
edg_acoustics/example_google.py

# matlab data files
*.mat
# !examples/*.mat
!examples/scenario1/*.mat

# test mesh files
data/tests/mesh/*
```


Main ingredients of using Git on your own [1]

1. Setting up a repository.
2. Saving changes
 - `git add/commit`
 - **Commit Often, Commit Small**
 - **Meaningful** commit message

<https://subscription.packtpub.com/book/application-development/9781789137545/1/ch01lv1sec13/the-three-stages>

Write good commit message

- Commit message is the best way to communicate **context** about a change to fellow developers (and indeed to **yourself** in the future).
 - Re-establishing the context of a piece of code is wasteful, and should be reduced as much as possible
- A “*git diff*” will tell you **what** changed, but only the commit message can properly tell you **why**.
- *A commit message shows whether a developer is a good collaborator.*

<https://www.conventionalcommits.org/en/v1.0.0/>

<https://cbea.ms/git-commit/#end>

Write good commit message

Semantic Commit Messages

See how a minor change to your commit message style can make you a better programmer.

Format: `<type>(<scope>): <subject>`

`<scope>` is optional

Example

```
feat: add hat wobble
^--^ ^-----^
|     |
|     +-> Summary in present tense.
|
+-----> Type: chore, docs, feat, fix, refactor, style, or test.
```

More Examples:

- `feat` : (new feature for the user, not a new feature for build script)
- `fix` : (bug fix for the user, not a fix to a build script)
- `docs` : (changes to the documentation)
- `style` : (formatting, missing semi colons, etc; no production code change)
- `refactor` : (refactoring production code, eg. renaming a variable)
- `test` : (adding missing tests, refactoring tests; no production code change)
- `chore` : (updating grunt tasks etc; no production code change)

<https://gist.github.com/joshbuckea/6f47e86d2510bce28f8e7f42ae84c716>

Main ingredients of using Git on your own [1]

1. Setting up a repository.
2. Saving changes
 - `git add/commit`
 - `git stash`:

<https://www.atlassian.com/git/tutorials/saving-changes/git-stash#stashing-your-work>

Main ingredients of using Git on your own [1]

1. Setting up a repository.
2. Saving changes
3. Exploring history
 - `git status/diff/checkout`
 - `git log -S "some text" -i`
 - `git grep`

Main ingredients of using Git on your own [1]

1. Setting up a repository.
2. Saving changes
3. Exploring history
4. Undoing changes
 - `git revert`
 - `git reset --soft --mixed(default) --hard`

<https://www.atlassian.com/git/tutorials/undoing-changes/git-reset>

Main ingredients of using Git on your own [1]

1. Setting up a repository.
2. Saving changes
3. Exploring history
4. Undoing changes
5. Rewriting history
 - `git commit --amend`
 - To modify the most recent commit
 - An entirely new commit is created
 - Don't amend public commits!

Main ingredients of using Git on your own [1]

1. Setting up a repository.
2. Saving changes
3. Exploring history
4. Undoing changes
5. Rewriting history
 - `git commit --amend`
 - `git reflog`: a log of where the tips of branches and other references were in your local repository, providing a history of your HEAD and reference movements
 - the safe net

```
4c9a506 (HEAD -> development) HEAD@{0}: checkout: moving from main to development
68efea3 (main) HEAD@{1}: checkout: moving from main_group to main
8530da9 (group-repo/main, main_group) HEAD@{2}: reset: moving to HEAD
8530da9 (group-repo/main, main_group) HEAD@{3}: commit: refactor: For scenario2, Adjust boundary conditions for hard wall material, frequency upper limit, and mesh approximation degree in main.py script
3f7d27b HEAD@{4}: commit: refactor: Update main.py script, adjust boundary conditions for hard wall material
```


Using Git collaboratively

- Git branches: a pointer to a snapshot of your changes. When you want to add a new feature or fix a bug—no matter how big or how small—you spawn a new branch to encapsulate your changes.
- <https://learngitbranching.js.org/>

```
Learn Git Branching
Hide Goal  Level Branch Spaghetti  Instructions
$ level advanced3
$ hint
Make sure to do everything in the proper order! Branch one first, then two, then three
$ delay 2000
$ show goal
$ show solution
$ reset --forSolution
$ git checkout one
$ git cherry-pick C4 C3 C2
$ git checkout two
$ git cherry-pick C5
C4 C3 C2
$ git branch -f three C2
$ reset
```


Using Git collaboratively

1. Setting up a remote repository.
 - Github/Gitlab/Bitbucket
2. Syncing
 - `git remote/fetch/push/pull`
3. Working with branches & conflicts
 - `git merge`
 - `git rebase`:
 - to process or combine a sequence of commits to a new base commit
 - to adapt a branch to incorporate the latest changes from another branch without yet merging this branch into the other branch
 - to maintain a linear project history
 - *git rebase -i* can be used to rewrite history

How to contribute to others' code [2]

- Open an issue in the repository you wish to contribute to
- In the issue, write a short proposal for your suggested change or new feature
- Motivate why and how you wish to do this
- Also indicate where you are unsure and where you would like feedback
- **Discuss and get feedback before you code**
- Once you start coding, indicate that you are working on it
- Once you are done, submit your new feature as pull request or merge request which references/closes the issue/proposal

- How about a collaborative project with multiple contributor? Owner or collaborator?

Outline

INTRODUCTION
(1MIN)

VERSION
CONTROL (5MIN)

CODE QUALITY
(5MIN)

The Zen of Python [6]


```
Beautiful is better than ugly.  
Explicit is better than implicit.  
Simple is better than complex.  
Complex is better than complicated.  
Flat is better than nested.  
Sparse is better than dense.  
Readability counts.  
Special cases aren't special enough to break the rules.  
Although practicality beats purity.  
Errors should never pass silently.  
Unless explicitly silenced.  
In the face of ambiguity, refuse the temptation to guess.  
There should be one-- and preferably only one --obvious way to do it.  
Although that way may not be obvious at first unless you're Dutch.  
Now is better than never.  
Although never is often better than *right* now.  
If the implementation is hard to explain, it's a bad idea.  
If the implementation is easy to explain, it may be a good idea.  
Namespaces are one honking great idea -- let's do more of those!
```


Modular Code

- Modularity:
 - dividing a software system into separate, interchangeable, independent components, each of which handles a specific aspect of the software's functionality.
 - Simple components build complex behavior.
 - Functions
 - classes
 - modules
 - libraries/packages
 - Programs
- Benefits:
 - Enhanced Maintainability
 - Simplified Debugging
 - Reusability
 - Scalability

Modular Code: how?

- Understand the problem
- Plan your architecture
 - identify key components
 - define interfaces

Modular Code: how?

- Understand the problem
- Plan your architecture
 - identify key components
 - define interfaces
- Each module or class should have responsibility over a single part of the functionality and that responsibility should be entirely encapsulated by the module
 - reducing complexity
 - increasing reusability
- Refactor regularly

Defensive programming

- Def: writing software that behaves **correctly** under a broad range of conditions by anticipating and managing possible errors and exceptions.
 - Validating inputs to prevent incorrect or harmful data from being processed.
 - Adding checks and controls throughout the code to catch errors or irregularities as early as possible.
 - Ensuring the program can handle unexpected situations gracefully.
 - Fail-Safe Defaults: Use safe default values that do not compromise system security in case of failure.
 - Assertions: Use assertions to catch unexpected conditions.

Defensive programming

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```
static check_BC_list(BC_list, mesh) \[source\]
```

Check if `BC_list` is compatible with `mesh`. Given a `mesh` with a set of boundary conditions specified in `mesh.BC_triangles`, check if the list of boundary conditions specification, `BC_list`, is compatible. By compatible we mean that all boundary conditions (keys) in `BC_list` exist in `mesh.BC_labels`, and vice-versa.

Parameters:

- `mesh` (`edg_acoustics.Mesh`) – see `mesh` .
- `BC_list` (`dict[str, int]`) – see `BC_list` .

Returns: `is_compatible` (`bool`) – a flag specifying if `BC_list` is compatible with the `mesh` or not.

Defensive programming

- Def: writing software that behaves **correctly** under a broad range of conditions by anticipating and managing possible errors and exceptions.
 - Fail-Safe Defaults: Use safe default values that do not compromise system security in case of failure.

```
edg_acoustics.time_integration.CFL_Default = 0.5 \[source\]
```

Default value of the CFL number for time integration schemes.

Type: `float`

```
class edg_acoustics.time_integration.TimeIntegrator(L_operator, dtscale, CFL=CFL_Default) \[source\]
```

Bases: `abc.ABC`

Base class for time integrators.

- Parameters:
- `L_operator` (*Callable*[[*numpy.ndarray*, *numpy.ndarray*, *numpy.ndarray*, *numpy.ndarray*, *list*]]) – the function in AcousticSimulation that enables the computation of Lq , given $q = [P, V_x, V_y, V_z]$
 - `dtscale` (*float*) – the time step scale based on the mesh size measure
 - `CFL` (*float*) – the CFL number

Defensive programming

- Def: writing software that behaves **correctly** under a broad range of conditions by anticipating and managing possible errors and exceptions.
 - Assertions: Use assertions to catch unexpected conditions.

static `check_BCpara(BCnode, BCpara, freq_max)` [\[source\]](#)

Check if BCpara is compatible with AcousticsSimulation.BCnode and satisfies physical admissibility condition.

Given an acoustics simulation data structure with a set of boundary conditions specified in acoustics_simulation.BCnode, check if the list of boundary conditions specification and parameters are compatible. By compatible we mean that all boundary conditions (keys) in BCpara exist in acoustics_simulation.BCnode, and vice-versa. Also, to satisfy the causality and reality conditions, multi-pole model parameters ζ_i (stored in first row of numpy.array BCpara[BC_label]) need to be positive. To satisfy the passivity condition, the magnitude of the reflection coefficient from the multi-pole model need to be smaller than 1, that is, $|R(\omega)| \leq 1$, where

$$R(\omega) \approx R_\infty + \sum_{k=1}^S \frac{A_k}{\zeta_k + i\omega} + \sum_{l=1}^T \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{B_l - iC_l}{\alpha_l - i\beta_l + i\omega} + \frac{B_l + iC_l}{\alpha_l + i\beta_l + i\omega} \right)$$

- Parameters:**
- **BCnode** (*list[dict]*) – see `edg_acoustics.AcousticsSimulation.BCnode`.
 - **BCpara** (*list[dict]*) – see `edg_acoustics.AbsorbBC.BCpara`.
 - **freq_max** (*float*) – maximum resolvable frequency of the simulation.
<default>: `edg_acoustics.boundary_condition.FREQ_MAX`
- Raises:**
- **AssertionError** – If BCpara.[index]['label'] is not present in the acoustics_simulation.BCnode.[index]['label'], an error is raised. If a label is present in the acoustics_simulation.BCnode.[index]['label'] but not in BCpara, an error is raised. If the labels in BCpara and BCnode are not the same, an error is raised.
 - **AssertionError** – If the reflection coefficient is not smaller than 1, an error is raised.
 - **AssertionError** – If the number of BC types is not the same in the BC_labels and BC_para, an error is raised.
 - **AssertionError** – If the causality and reality conditions are not met, an error is raised.

Enhancing Code Quality by Static Code Analysis

- Static code analysis is a method that examines code and detects software vulnerabilities **before** your code is executed or the project is built and deployed. [5]
- This analysis is capable of identifying quality issues, including security weaknesses and errors. In addition to finding bugs, many of these tools can also help maintain a consistent coding style. [5]

Enhancing Code Quality by Static Code Analysis

Language	Static code analysis tool
C/C++	Cppcheck, cpplint
Python	Pylint, prospector
Javascript	ESLint, JSLint, JSHint
Java	Checkstyle, FindBugs, PMD
Perl	PerlTidy
R	lintr
Shell/Bash	shellcheck

Enhancing Code Quality by Static Code Analysis


```
PROBLEMS 804 OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TER
> acoustics_simulation.py edg_acoustics 602
> boundary_condition.py edg_acoustics 79
> preprocessing.py edg_acoustics 10
> initial_condition.py edg_acoustics 10
> mesh.py edg_acoustics 100
> ex_01.py examples
```

```
PROBLEMS 804 OUTPUT DEBUG CONSOLE TERMINAL PORTS GITLENS
boundary_condition.py edg_acoustics 79
  Line too long (110/100) Pylint(C0301:line-too-long) [Ln 206, Col 1]
  Attribute name "BCpara" doesn't conform to snake_case naming style Pylint(C0103:invalid-name) [Ln 211, Col 9]
  Attribute name "BCvar" doesn't conform to snake_case naming style Pylint(C0103:invalid-name) [Ln 212, Col 9]
  Line too long (119/100) Pylint(C0301:line-too-long) [Ln 214, Col 1]
  Line too long (120/100) Pylint(C0301:line-too-long) [Ln 215, Col 1]
preprocessing.py edg_acoustics 10
  Number of parameters was 1 in 'Flux.FluxP' and is now 5 in overriding 'UpwindFlux.FluxP' method Pylint(W0221:arguments-differ) [Ln 67, Col 5]
  Number of parameters was 1 in 'Flux.FluxVx' and is now 5 in overriding 'UpwindFlux.FluxVx' method Pylint(W0221:arguments-differ) [Ln 76, Col 5]
  Number of parameters was 1 in 'Flux.FluxVy' and is now 5 in overriding 'UpwindFlux.FluxVy' method Pylint(W0221:arguments-differ) [Ln 85, Col 5]
  Number of parameters was 1 in 'Flux.FluxVz' and is now 5 in overriding 'UpwindFlux.FluxVz' method Pylint(W0221:arguments-differ) [Ln 94, Col 5]
  First line empty in module docstring Pylint(C0199:docstring-first-line-empty) [Ln 1, Col 1]
  Line too long (122/100) Pylint(C0301:line-too-long) [Ln 6, Col 1]
  Method name "FluxP" doesn't conform to snake_case naming style Pylint(C0103:invalid-name) [Ln 31, Col 5]
  Method name "FluxVx" doesn't conform to snake_case naming style Pylint(C0103:invalid-name) [Ln 35, Col 5]
  Method name "FluxVy" doesn't conform to snake_case naming style Pylint(C0103:invalid-name) [Ln 39, Col 5]
```


Enhancing Code Quality by Static Code Analysis

Problematic code:

```
class Unicorn:
    def __init__(self, fluffiness_level):
        if self.fluffiness_level > 9000: # [access-member-before-definition]
            print("It's OVER-FLUFFYYYY ! *crush glasses*")
        self.fluffiness_level = fluffiness_level
```

Correct code:

```
class Unicorn:
    def __init__(self, fluffiness_level):
        self.fluffiness_level = fluffiness_level
        if self.fluffiness_level > 9000:
            print("It's OVER-FLUFFYYYY ! *crush glasses*")
```

Problematic code:

```
def add(x, y): # [differing-param-doc]
    """Add two numbers.

    :param int x: x value.
    :param int z: z value.
    """

    return x + y
```

Correct code:

```
def add(x, y):
    """Add two numbers.

    :param int x: x value.
    :param int y: y value.
    """

    return x + y
```


Code Review in Maintaining High Standards

- Code review is a systematic examination of source code intended to find and fix mistakes, improve the software, and ensure that coding conventions are being followed.
- Tools and Platforms
 - GitHub's pull request review mechanism, which allows multiple team members to comment on, suggest, or approve modifications."
- Best Practices:
 - Clear guidelines: follow a set [checklist](#) that includes checking for logical errors, optimization, and adherence to project coding standards.
 - Constructive feedback: aimed at knowledge sharing and mutual improvement rather than criticism.

Rubrics for assessing code quality [5]

Level	1	2	3	4
names	names appear unreadable, meaningless or misleading	names accurately describe the intent of the code, but can be incomplete, lengthy, misspelled or inconsistent use of casing	names accurately describe the intent of the code, and are complete, distinctive, concise, correctly spelled and consistent use of casing	all names in the program use a consistent vocabulary
headers	headers are generally missing or descriptions are redundant or obsolete; use mixed languages or are misspelled	header comments are generally present; summarize the goal of parts of the program and how to use those; but may be somewhat inaccurate or incomplete	header comments are generally present; accurately summarize the role of parts of the program and how to use those; but may still be wordy	header comments are generally present; contain only essential explanations, information and references
comments	comments are generally missing, redundant or obsolete; use mixed languages or are misspelled	comments explain code and potential problems, but may be wordy	comments explain code and potential problems, are concise	comments are only present where strictly needed
layout	old commented out code is present or lines are generally too long to read	positioning of elements within source files is not optimized for readability	positioning of elements within source files is optimized for readability	positioning of elements is consistent between files and in line with platform conventions

Rubrics for assessing code quality [5]

formatting	formatting is missing or misleading	indentation, line breaks, spacing and brackets highlight the intended structure but erratically	indentation, line breaks, spacing and brackets consistently highlight the intended structure	formatting makes similar parts of code clearly identifiable
flow	there is deep nesting; code performs more than one task per line; unreachable code is present	flow is complex or contains many exceptions or jumps; parts of code are duplicate	flow is simple and contains few exceptions or jumps; duplication is very limited	in the case of exceptions or jumps, the most common path through the code is clearly visible
idiom	control structures are customized in a misleading way	choice of control structures is inappropriate	choice of control structures is appropriate; reuse of library functionality may be limited	reuse of library functionality and generic data structures where possible
expressions	expressions are repeated or contain unnamed constants	expressions are complex or long; data types are inappropriate	expressions are simple; data types are appropriate	expressions are all essential for control flow
decomposition	most code is in one or a few big routines; variables are reused for different purposes	most routines are limited in length but mix tasks; routines share many variables instead of having parameters	routines perform a limited set of tasks divided into parts; use of shared variables is limited	routines perform a very limited set of tasks and the number of parameters and shared variables is limited
modularization	most code is in one or a few large modules; or modules are artificially separated	modules have mixed responsibilities, contain many variables or contain many routines	modules have clearly defined responsibilities, contain few variables and a somewhat limited amount of routines	modules are defined such that communication between them is limited

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DOCUMENTATION
(2 MIN)

Documentation

- A good lesson on **How to document your research software** is given by [CodeRefinery](#).
- Core Sphinx extensions and setup used for DG_RoomAcoustics:
 - sphinx.ext.autodoc: For pulling documentation from docstrings.
 - sphinx.ext.napoleon: For supporting Google and NumPy style docstrings.
 - sphinx.ext.viewcode: To include links to the source code of documented Python objects.
 - autoapi.extension: Automatically generate API documentation from the source code.
 - intersphinx_mapping: link to external projects' documentation, enhancing the comprehensiveness of the docs.
 - customized CSS: Integration of custom styles via *html_css_files* to enhance the visual appearance of the documentation.
- Use cross-referencing

Next workshop:

References

1. <https://www.atlassian.com/git/tutorials/what-is-version-control>
2. <https://coderefinery.github.io/git-collaborative/concepts/>
3. <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/index.html>
4. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2999541.2999555>
5. <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/reproducible-research/code-quality.html>
6. <https://peps.python.org/pep-0020/#the-zen-of-python>

Thank you

